

IMPROVEMENT OF METHODS AND MEANS OF RAPID NOTIFICATION OF POSSIBLE FIRES IN BUILDINGS AND CONSTRUCTIONS

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Abstract. *This article presents a rapid fire detection algorithm based on modern technologies and artificial intelligence systems for rapid reporting of fires occurring in open and classified areas. Also, early warning software for buildings and structures was developed and complex visual images were analyzed. The proposed system quickly detects fire outbreaks using video cameras at 360 degrees and, unlike other notification systems, quickly detects fire outbreaks at a distance of 40-50 meters and provides information about the warning signal.*

Keywords: *fire, open cv, detector, monitoring, forecasting, convolutional, neural, deep learning, artificial intelligence, CNN, AlexNet, YOLO.*

The fire detection approach involves three steps: motion detection, fire detection, and area classification. Initially, moving objects are detected from video images using background subtraction [1].

Early detection of fire can effectively prevent the spread of fire and reduce the damage caused by fire. In indoor environments, various smoke detectors and fire detectors are widely used to report potential fires. However, in this process, software sensors have a number of limitations. They require proximity to fire sources to operate in outdoor environments. In addition, they typically require smoke from a fire to occur and then burn for a period of time to trigger the alarm, and cannot provide information about the location and size of the fire. There are hundreds of video cameras installed in buildings and structures, and several surveillance screens in the control room [2].

The application of deep convolutional neural networks (CNN) in computer vision, such as image restoration, classification, localization, segmentation, and detection, is considered very effective [6, 7, 9, 13].

The main idea behind CNN is to solve the problem by gradually breaking it down into smaller parts until a solution is found. By feeding the model from the raw pixel values to the classifier, we can avoid the common complex processing steps. The basic model of a CNN is a multi-layer feed-forward network with convolutional and sub-layers. The deepest layers of a CNN are used for classification based on large-scale reasoning. Here we will look at what each layer means [13].

In convolutional layers, the image (input) undergoes convolutional processes, and then the resulting data is passed to the next layer. Each node in a convolutional layer contains receptive fields formed from units in the layers below it. The neurons in these areas include basic visual features such as corners, endpoints, and directed edges. Many of the feature maps in this layer can extract multiple features. All units in a given feature map are the same, ensuring that the identified

features are applied equally to all inputs. Researchers have used this formula (1) to describe the shape of a convolutional layer [10, 13].

$$x_j^l = f \left[\sum_{i \in M_j} x_i^{l-1} * k_{ij}^l + b_i^l \right] \quad (1)$$

In convolutional layers, the input maps collection is denoted by M_j , where k is the kernel size determining the extent of convolution applied to the image. Additionally, b represents a bias, and x_j^l denotes the output as the j th feature map of that convolutional layer.

The pooling and subsampling layer plays a crucial role in reducing the complexity of the feature map's resolution by performing sub-sampling and local averaging. This layer is responsible for down sampling the convolutional layer's output, which reduces the computation required for subsequent layers.

The appearance of the lower sampling layer is determined by the following formula (2) [10].

$$x_j^l = f \left[\beta_{jdown}^l (x_i^{l-1}) + b_i^l \right] \quad (2)$$

where (down) refers to a process that is known as sub-sampling. In most cases, the sub-sampling (down) function will offer an n -by- n block to calculate the final output in the input picture. This will result in a normalized output and n times smaller than the original. Where b represents the additive bias and represents the multiplicative bias.

The CNN model used in this paper is based on the Alex Net design, which has been shown to be effective in rapid fire detection with a few minor modifications adapted from experiments. [11] To reduce complexity, we limited the number of output neurons to just two. The model consists of ten layers, including five convolutional layers, five max pooling layers, and two fully connected layers, each with a total length of 4096. Given an input image x of dimensions $H \times W \times C$, where H , W , and C represent the height, width, and depth of the image, respectively, a filter (also known as a kernel) w of dimensions $h \times w \times c$ is applied to extract generic features from the image. $(H - h + 1) \times (W - w + 1) \times F$ is produced by the following mathematical operation presented (3):

$$y_{i,j,f} = \sum_{k=0}^{h-1} \sum_{l=0}^{w-1} \sum_{m=0}^{c-1} x_{i+k,j+l,m} * w_{k,l,m,f} \quad (3)$$

Here i denotes the height index of the feature map, the width index is indicated by j , and f is used for depth. Similarly, the height, width, and depth index for a filter are represented by k , l , and m , respectively.

In addition, we first swapped the order of the max pooling and normalization layers between the first and second convolutional layers and moved them to the fifth position. Max pooling is a downscaling process that reduces the spatial dimensions of the feature map while preserving the most important features. A pooling filter of size $(H \times W \times C)$ is used to preserve the maximum value of each field. Formula (4) gives the mathematical formula for max pooling [13].

$$y_{i,j,f} = \max_{k=0}^{h-1} \max_{l=0}^{w-1} y_{i,s+k,s+l,f} \quad (4)$$

Here, i denotes the height index of the feature map after merging, the width index is denoted by j , and f denotes the depth. Similarly, the height, width, and depth indices for the merging filter are denoted by k , l , and m , respectively. We use a SoftMax classifier to identify the top causes in the last layer of the classification system. Nonlinearity is very important for neural networks, and

this is achieved by using activation functions. One such function is the rectified linear unit function (ReLU), which is widely used due to its efficiency. Another variation of ReLU, the ReLU activation function, introduces a small positive slope for negative inputs, thereby solving the problem of dead neurons that can occur with ReLU [13].

Mathematically, the activation function of the inactive ReLU is calculated using the formula (5).

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} x & \text{if } x > 0 \\ ax & \text{if } x \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where x is the input to the activation function, y is the output, and a is a small positive slope for negative inputs.

The final part of the CNN is the fully connected layers, which perform the final classification of the input image. Given an input x of size n , a fully connected layer is a matrix multiplication of the input and a weight matrix w of size $x \times m$ followed by an activation function. The operation that defines a fully connected layer can be expressed mathematically (6).

$$y = f(w \cdot x + b) \quad (6)$$

Here, f is the activation function, b is the bending term, and y is the output of the fully coupled layer. Common activation functions in fully connected layers include sigmoid, ReLU, and SoftMax functions. Activation functions in a convolutional neural network (CNN) play a crucial role in determining the output of the network. The "sigma" function is typically used to map input values between 0 and 1, while the "ReLU" function is used to convert negative input values to 0 and positive input values to their original value. The SoftMax function is used in the last layer of the CNN to classify the input image by computing the exponential of each input value and then normalizing the result to form a probability distribution over the classes. The class with the highest probability is the final output of the CNN.

This means that images from only a few cameras can be analyzed at the same time, and images from other cameras have to be displayed sequentially. It can take tens of minutes to display all the cameras. During this time, fire events can occur and be missed by the operator responsible for viewing the monitoring screens. In addition, operators have other tasks, such as monitoring control systems. Therefore, there is a demand for the development of new software tools to automatically detect fire hazards.

With the rapid development of digital technology and artificial intelligence technology, intelligent image technology fire detection methods are being proposed in some fields. Fire detection using smart technologies is carried out in two stages. Initially, fire detection is done using a color model and some hand-crafted features [12].

This focuses on the color and shape characteristics of the fire. Fire detection methods in surveillance cameras determine the problem by creating a database and classifying it into a "fire" or "non-fire" class.

The video stream capture and background removal are performed by OpenCV, an open-source object recognition library. Picture 1 illustrates the entire background removal process. First, the Gaussian method is applied to the original frames of a single video stream to remove image noise (see Picture 1a). Then, the CNN-based background removal is performed in Picture 1a. We can detect the moving object (such as fire and people), which is the white areas in Picture 1b. But we can find that there are some gray areas in Picture 1b (in the green circle), so we binarize this image and mark the moving object with white color in Picture 1c. Finally, the morphology closure

operation is used to merge the small discrete regions into a complete region (in the red circle). Thus, the entire moving object is detected in picture 1d [3, 4].

Picture 1a. Gauss method

Picture 1b. CNN-based background subtraction

Picture 1c. Binarization

Picture 1d. Closure

In the fire detection approach, we calculate the size of the white areas in the entire frame. We set the region boundaries and if the size of the white areas (moving objects) exceeds the boundary, the next detection steps are performed.

The fire detection model is developed using the YOLO method, where YOLO decomposes object detection into discrete bounding boxes and their associated class probabilities as a regression problem. This technique is used to separate bounding boxes and images into classes directly from images in a single evaluation of a single neural network, such as a CNN model. The Yolo model is designed to detect several objects, but fire detection is the detection of a single object (fire).

To input the image into the CNN for traffic detection, the image size must be changed to 416×416 pixels. The YOLO model divides the input image into an $S \times S$ grid (see picture 2). In the YOLO model, for each cell, k bounding boxes predict three parts (bounding boxes, of different widths and heights): coordinates, confidence scores, and conditional class probabilities.

Picture 2. Yolo model

Early detection of fires makes it possible to reduce the losses caused by fires in various regions.

The program we created was written in Python and is defined using the OpenCV library and the YOLO model.

We load the following fires into the created program and get the results (picture 2a, picture 2b)

Picture 2a. Video to be uploaded to the application

The program produces the following result (Picture 3a).

Picture 3a: Fire detection using software

Picture 2a. Fire detection using software

Picture 3b. Fire detection using software

The program took 1 second to detect a fire at a distance of up to 2 meters.

The table below shows the results of tests on detecting fires at different distances, with a table and graph of changes over distance and time.

Distance (meters)	1-2	3-4	5-10	10-15	15-30	30-40	40-60
Time (seconds)	1	1,5	2	2.5	3	3.5	3-4

The data graph in the table above is:

The created program, by processing images from continuously captured video footage, confirms that the suspected event is a fire, provides information about fire parameters, and issues a fire warning signal at the monitored facility.

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